

Clocks & particles in a centrifugal field

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ABSTRACT

We are proposing a new approach to investigate the physical effects of the centrifugal acceleration in an inertial reference system. Our proposal is based primarily on geometrical considerations, built on the extension of the equivalence principle. The equivalence principle is then used to derive an effective Schwarzschild radius. After having developed the equations, we propose an experiment to detect the effect of the centrifugal acceleration on the time. We compute also the consequence on the unstable particle's lifetime. The testability of our model is well reachable from our present technology.

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Introduction

In General Relativity the mass bends the space–time. One of the consequence of the theory is that, the time, is slowing down in the presence of a gravitational field.

In 1960, Pound and Rebka [1], made the first experiment to test the frequency shift of the electromagnetic radiation, induced by a variation of the gravitational potential.

The results confirmed the prediction of General Relativity. The time is affected by the gravity: the more intense the gravitational field is, the more the time is slowing down.

The experiment opened also a new sector of investigation to verify how, the time, reacts to the motion in a gravitational field.

Recently, a new paper, has been published by Wen-Te Liao and Sven Ahrens [2] where, they suggest, an experiment to measure the light–matter interaction in a centrifugal field.

Here, we propose, to extend the equivalence principle to the centrifugal acceleration in order to get an effective Schwarzschild solution and to perform an experiment able to directly measure the relativistic effects on the time.

First, we will develop the equations based on identical clocks mounted on a long arm centrifugal machine, to apply then the equations to the case of radioactive elements.

The present experiment, may be consider both a Gedanken experiment and, since it is also feasible, a possible real experiment. The experiment requires a long-arm centrifugal machine, very much similar the one used to train pilots to the \vec{g} acceleration.

Two synchronized atomic clocks, at the time t_0 have to be assembled on the arm of the centrifugal machine. Clocks 1 and 2 shall be, respectively, fixed at 10 and 5 m from the center.

The radial acceleration vector, pointing to the center of mass is considered positive while, the radial acceleration, pointing in the opposite direction, is negative.

Centripetal acceleration

A point P is moving in a circular path at a constant tangential speed. The inertial reference frame system is fixed at the center of the circumference, of radius r and module R . For sake of simplicity, the point P_2 is on the axis x .

The tangential velocity of the point P , due its continuous change of direction, is subject to an acceleration $\vec{a} = d\vec{v}/dt$ where $d\vec{v}$ and dt are infinitesimal intervals equal to:

$$d\vec{v} = \vec{v}_2 - \vec{v}_1 \quad \text{and} \quad dt = dt_2 - dt_1. \quad (1)$$

The module of the vector $d\vec{v}$ is given by the relation:

$$\|d\vec{v}\| = 2\|\vec{v}\|\sin\frac{\|d\vec{\phi}\|}{2}. \quad (2)$$

For an infinitesimal time interval dt also the module of $d\vec{\phi}$ is infinitesimal such that, if the angle $\sin d\phi \simeq d\phi$ and it is in radians, the arc of circumference $\vec{P}_1\vec{P}_2$ can be considered equal to the chord $\vec{P}_1\vec{P}_2$:

$$\|d\vec{v}\| \simeq \|\vec{v}\|\|d\vec{\phi}\|, \quad (3)$$

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$$\vec{a} = \vec{v} \frac{d\vec{\phi}}{dt} = \vec{v}\vec{\omega}, \quad (4)$$

where $\vec{\omega} = d\vec{\phi}/dt$ is the uniform angular velocity vector in radians per second and, as $\vec{\omega} = \vec{v}/r$:

$$\vec{a} = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2}{R} \hat{r} = \|\vec{\omega}\|^2 R \hat{r}, \quad (5)$$

$$\|\vec{a}\| = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2}{R} = \|\vec{\omega}\|^2 R. \quad (6)$$

The coordinates (x, y) of the vectors are:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{v_1} \\ y_{v_1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin d\phi \\ \cos d\phi \end{pmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{v_2} \\ y_{v_2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{dv} \\ y_{dv} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin d\phi \\ 1 - \cos d\phi \end{pmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where $d\vec{v} = d\vec{v}_2 - d\vec{v}_1$. From the vector analysis (Fig. 1) we see that the acceleration $(d\vec{v}/dt)$ is pointing to the center.

In an inertial reference system, the acceleration vector is centripetal but, to study the phenomenology of the centrifugal acceleration, it is necessary to move the reference frame system in P . In its reference frame system, the point P is considered at rest while the reference system (x, y) , is rotating in the opposite direction. If the motion is counterclockwise in an inertial reference system, in a noninertial reference system the motion will be clockwise (or vice versa). The radial acceleration points outward of the circumference.

The acceleration change sign and becomes centrifugal (or negative).

Centrifugal acceleration

To change the reference system in P , the orientation of the vectors shall point in the opposite direction. The transformation is specular. To transform the vectors of π , the matrices have to be multiplied by -1 (Fig. 2) [3]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x'_{v_1} \\ y'_{v_1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sin d\phi \\ \cos d\phi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin d\phi \\ -\cos d\phi \end{pmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x'_{v_2} \\ y'_{v_2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x'_{dv} \\ y'_{dv} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin d\phi \\ 1 - \cos d\phi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin d\phi \\ \cos d\phi - 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where $d\vec{v}' = d\vec{v}'_2 - d\vec{v}'_1$. It is necessary to compute the effect of the centrifugal force in a noninertial reference frame since, otherwise, it would not be possible to keep it in due account, the antagonist effects between gravity and centrifugal acceleration.

However it is not more than an expedient, as the Newton's third law is only valid for an inertial reference frames [4, ch. 2, 10], and this is not the case.

From the other side, the theory of General Relativity has been built on the assumption that Nature's laws must be the same for any observer, including in a noninertial reference frame system, just where the gravity is at work.

The first exact solution to the Einstein's equations was found by Schwarzschild [5] in the 1916, but it does not give any explicit

Fig. 1. Vector analysis of the centripetal acceleration. The vector $d\vec{v}$ points to the center. The amplitude of the angle $d\phi$ has been exaggerated for graphical reasons.

Fig. 2. Vector analysis of the centrifugal acceleration. The reference system x', y' is comoving with P . The vector $d\vec{v}'$ in a non-inertial reference system, points in the opposite direction of the center c and, according to P , it is the reference system x, y to rotate, while P is at rest.

indications about how to keep into consideration the effects of the centrifugal acceleration.

It is then interesting to note that, it is not strictly necessary to change the orientation of the vectors \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2 . It is possible to get the same result of Eq. (12) by exchanging the events order of Eq. (9), $d\vec{v}' = d\vec{v}_1 - d\vec{v}_2$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x'_{dv} \\ y'_{dv} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin d\phi \\ \cos d\phi \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin d\phi \\ \cos d\phi - 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Of course, it is not the algebra or the geometric construction to be so interesting, but the fact that Nature is consistent with it. The vector $d\vec{v}$ is transformed into $d\vec{v}'$. The time direction $(t_1 - t_2)$ becomes negative.

In such a way, it is possible to apply the Schwarzschild solution from an inertial reference frame.

It seems to be reasonable to think that, in an infinitesimal amount of time, small enough to approximate the space-time as flat, the time evolution is undetermined. As long as the space-time can be considered flat, there is not any privileged time direction to follow.

Therefore, when the space-time is flat and the time arrow cannot be determined, whether or not the reference frame system is, or is not inertial, cannot make any difference.

Only leaving the system free to evolve, and summing all the infinitesimal time lengths, or integrating the proper time (τ) over the time (t), it is possible to appreciate the space–time curvature and if it is, or it is not, in an inertial reference system.

Due to the fact that the centrifugal acceleration (\vec{a}_{cf}) is acting in opposition to the centripetal acceleration ($-\vec{g}$), in an inertial reference system, a negative acceleration or, a repulsive acceleration field (\vec{g}), can be considered equivalent to the centrifugal acceleration field in a noninertial reference system, provided that we consider an infinitesimal amount of time, or an ‘instantaneous rest frame’.

For instance, if we look at a movie in the reverse mode and we see a meteor it is decelerating from the Earth to the space, we know that something must be wrong because gravity is always positive but, for sure, we cannot say the singles frames of the movie are wrong. They are always the same frames that we look at when the movie is playing in the normal mode. Even the world line of the motion is the same. What makes the difference is just the temporal arrow, or the evolution of the geodesic.

The strategy then, to calculate the behavior of the space–time curvature caused by a centrifugal field, will be to evaluate the space–time curvature by reversing the time arrow, thanks to the Schwarzschild metric, from the center of the reference frame system (x, y). In this way it is not necessary to modify the Schwarzschild matrix as follows:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 - r_s & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{(1-r_s)} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -r^2 \sin^2 \theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} -1 + r_s & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & +r^2 \sin^2 \theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

and get a negative solution under the square root (the terms g_{22} and g_{33} are zero as in the limit of examined case, $dr = 0$ and $d\theta = 0$).

The approach to reverse the time arrow is not new, as it was adopted for the first time by Feynman [6,7] to solve the electron–positron scattering and, more in general, between matter and virtual quanta.

By exchanging the event orders, a positive gravitational field is transformed into negative, while the equivalence principle is extended also to the case of the centrifugal/centripetal acceleration.

An intuitive explanation to the negative gravitational field, can be suggested by pure geometrical consideration, by using the geodesic line of a ray of light in an accelerated field, in analogy to the Einstein’s Gedanken experiment.

Let us consider the thought experiment of the Einstein’s elevator, extended also to the case of the centrifugal acceleration (Fig. 3):

Case (a): the elevator is at rest on the Earth. If we let drop an object, it will fall down in the direction of the floor toward the center of mass of our planet. The same situation may happen inside a rocket, if it is accelerating in the outer space, very far from any mass and any gravitational influence.

If the acceleration of the rocket, in the outer space, is of 9.8 m/s^2 , it is not possible to say whether or not we are accelerating inside a rocket or, as an alternative, we are at rest inside an elevator on our planet.

Fig. 3. Sketch of the equivalence principle. The space–time curvature is visible thanks to the bending of light. The centrifugal acceleration is bending the light in the opposite direction of a gravitational field. Case (a): Bending of light in a gravitational field. The elevator is at rest. The beam of light is bent toward the center of mass. Case (b): An observer, comoving in a centrifugal field, will see the light bent from the acceleration. The beam of light diverges from the center.

The pressure of the floor against our feet, due to the acceleration, is the same in both cases. In both cases, a ray of light, will be bent by the acceleration against the floor.

The gravity, or the continuous increasing of the velocity over the time, are causing the same effect.

Case (b): now we can repeat the same experience but, this time, the elevator is moving in circle at a constant speed, tied by a rope to a fixed point.

This time is the continuous change of direction that is acting against our inertia and pushes the floor against our feet.

If we measure the same light curvature of the case (a), we can then say that we are subject to the same acceleration.

So, apparently the situation is the same but, there is a difference that is relevant.

In the case (a), when we are subject to a gravitational field, our feet are pointing to the center of mass while, in the case (b), our feet are pointing in the opposite direction.

It means that the ray of light, in the case (b), is bent in the opposite direction respect to the center.

It is therefore necessary to consider an anti-gravitational field, of opposite sign to the gravitational one, to keep in due account the proper light curvature.

To make the proper calculation from an inertial reference system, having the origin in the center of the axis (x, y), we must determine an equivalent amount of mass to insert into the metric.

The magnitude of the gravitational mass will be determined thanks to the equivalence principle.

The equivalent amount of gravitational mass is necessary to describe the space–time curvature or, a negative gravitational field. This virtual mass is relevant for the space–time geometry in the empty space, not for the mass that is always positive.

$$\left\| \frac{Gm_1 m_2}{R^2} \hat{r} \right\| = m \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2}{R}, \quad (16)$$

where m_1 is the central mass expressed in kg and m_2 is an equivalent mass to m .

$$\|\vec{v}\| = \sqrt{\frac{Gm_1}{R}}, \quad (17)$$

$$m_1 = \frac{\|\vec{a}\| R^2}{G} = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2 R}{G}. \quad (18)$$

Hereafter we will use the notation (*) to refer to the virtual mass and/or to the time of the centrifugal acceleration. Let us make a short computation for clocks 1 and 2 in the case of a centrifugal

machine, having an arm of 10 m and, a constant angular velocity $\omega = 3 \text{ rad/s}$, equal to a tangential speed of 30 m/s at 10 m (clock 1) and 15 m/s at 5 m (clock 2)¹:

$$\text{clock 1} \quad \|\vec{a}_{cf}\| = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2}{R_1} = 90 \text{ m/s}^2 \quad \left(\text{clock 2} = \frac{1}{2} \text{ clock 1} \right), \quad (19)$$

$$\text{clock 1} \quad m_1^* = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2 R_1}{G} \approx 1.35 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ kg} \quad \left(\text{clock 2} = \frac{1}{8} \text{ clock 1} \right), \quad (20)$$

$$\text{clock 1} \quad r_{s_1}^* = \frac{2Gm_1^*}{c^2} \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m} \quad \left(\text{clock 2} = \frac{1}{8} \text{ clock 1} \right). \quad (21)$$

The metric sign convention of the Schwarzschild solution is (+ - - -) and $r_s = 2GM/c^2$:

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 - \frac{r^2}{c^2} d\theta^2 - \frac{r^2}{c^2} \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2. \quad (22)$$

Here, it is considered a circular path on the $x - y$ plane at a constant velocity, and therefore dr^2 and $d\theta^2$ are equal to 0, while the angle $d\phi^2 = \omega^2 dt^2$:

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) dt^2 - \frac{r^2}{c^2} d\phi^2, \quad (23)$$

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}\right), \quad (24)$$

$$d\tau = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}} dt, \quad (25)$$

$$d\tau = \pm dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}, \quad (26)$$

where $dt = t_2 - t_1$ and $-dt = t_1 - t_2$. It is now fixed and evaluated the $\Delta\tau$ parameter (Fig. 4):

$$1\text{st } (dt > 0): \quad \Delta\tau_{(-)} = dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}} - dt, \quad (27)$$

$$2\text{nd } (dt < 0): \quad \Delta\tau_{(+)} = -dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}} + dt. \quad (28)$$

For an orbiting body it is easy to note how, the two General Relativity solutions, are mutually cancelled. The space-time curvatures are symmetrical, $d\tau_{(+)} + d\tau_{(-)} = 0$, as expected for a free fall body (Fig. 5). As a consequence, for an orbiting body in free fall, the space-time is locally flat and, the proper time $d\tau$, is recovered by the Special Relativity theory, from the case of a rotating disk:

$$d\tau' = dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}. \quad (29)$$

The signature of the time arrow, cannot be defined in the frame of the Special Relativity theory since the space-time is flat by definition. From the other side, the General Relativity equations already include the effect, therefore, we are going to ignore the Special Relativity in a curved space-time [8].

It is also interesting to note as Fig. 4 is proposing two time dimensions: the top-down given by the space-time curvature and, the left-right, given by the entropy direction. We should also consider the fact that entropy and curvature have to evolve together, even if, for the entropy, the sign can never be changed.

Fig. 4. A preliminary sketch of the antagonist action between the centripetal and centrifugal acceleration on the time. The full details will be discussed and illustrated in the latest section, Fig. 7. The measures are not in scale.

Fig. 5. The centrifugal acceleration cancels out the centripetal one. Top elevator: Bending of light in a gravitational field. The elevator is at rest. The beam of light converges to the center. Below elevator: An orbiting body in a circular path, does not experience any gravitational acceleration. The centripetal and centrifugal acceleration cancel out mutually. The body is in free fall.

When the space-time is flat, the time loses one dimension, and the difference between a noninertial/inertial reference system apparently disappears.

The experiment needs to last for at least 3 days in order to get a discrepancy of some nanoseconds (Δt in seconds = $3600 \cdot 24 \cdot 3 = 259,200 \text{ s}$):

$$\text{clock 1:} \quad \Delta\tau_{1(+)}^* = -dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_{s_1}^*}{r_1} - \frac{\omega^2 r_1^2}{c^2}} + dt \approx 3.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}, \quad (30)$$

$$\text{clock 2:} \quad \Delta\tau_{2(+)}^* = -dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_{s_2}^*}{r_2} - \frac{\omega^2 r_2^2}{c^2}} + dt \approx 9.9 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}. \quad (31)$$

Since according to the current theory, the expected time dilation should be caused by the special relativity only, we need to compare the discrepancies:

$$\text{clock 1:} \quad \Delta\tau'_{1(-)} = dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2 r_1^2}{c^2}} - dt \approx -1.3 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}, \quad (32)$$

$$\text{clock 2:} \quad \Delta\tau'_{2(-)} = dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2 r_2^2}{c^2}} - dt \approx -3.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}. \quad (33)$$

¹ $c = 299,792,458 \text{ ms}^{-1}$; $G = 6.67259 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$

The discrepancy between the proper time $d\tau^*$ of clock 1 and 2, after three days, will be equal to the difference found for $\Delta\tau_1^* - \Delta\tau_2^*$ and so, it is possible to predict that, the difference of the two clocks, will be the double of the effect caused by the special relativity only.

The space–time curvature delays the time both in the case of the centrifugal or gravitational acceleration so, it is not possible to distinguish if the delay of the clock 1 compared to the clock 2, has been caused by a negative or positive curvature. The only thing it is possible to measure, is the difference.

$$\Delta\tau_1^* - \Delta\tau_2^* : D^* = 3.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s} - 9.9 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s} \simeq 2.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}, \quad (34)$$

$$\Delta\tau_1' - \Delta\tau_2' : D' = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s} - 3.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s} \simeq 9.3 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}, \quad (35)$$

$$D^* - D' = 2.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s} - 9.3 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s} \simeq 1.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}. \quad (36)$$

The difference between D^* and D' is crucial for the following reasons:

1. If the centrifugal force does not imply any virtual mass, the value of $\Delta\tau_1 - \Delta\tau_2$ should be about 1/3 of the prediction: $1.3 \cdot 10^{-9} - 3.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \simeq -9.3 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}$.
2. If the value is in agreement with the prediction ($\Delta\tau_1 - \Delta\tau_2 \sim 2.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}$), also the hypothesis of a negative time must be true. This is evident by the fact that, the module $\|\vec{g}\|$, of the gravitational acceleration, must diminish in presence of a centrifugal field. We can convince ourself this is the case by taking into consideration the effect of the centrifugal force on the equator line of our planet, where it is stronger. The gravitational acceleration, at the equator, is decreased by the action of the centrifugal acceleration and, therefore, in such coordinates we can consider the total mass of our planet less an equivalent virtual mass (m^*). In such a case, as we are evaluating the gravity in the frame of a classical Newtonian gravity, where the time is not included into the equations, the virtual mass can be considered as negative. If the net gravitational mass is reduced, it is immediate to reach the conclusion that even the curvature of the space–time must be reduced.

The values used in the present calculation are merely indicative. Less performance machines may be equally usable by simply increasing the running time.

It is also possible to calculate the theoretical difference of time dilation due to the centrifugal acceleration of a point P at rest at the equator of our planet. We consider a time interval $dt = 3600 \text{ s}$:

$$m_{ET}^* = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2 R}{G} \simeq 2.05 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ kg}, \quad (37)$$

where $\|\vec{v}\| = \frac{2\pi}{T} R \simeq 463 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, $T = 86,400 \text{ s}$ and $R = 6.371 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}$.

$$\text{Earth} : \Delta\tau_{ET(+)}^* = -dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_{sET}^*}{r_3} - \frac{\omega^2 r_3^2}{c^2}} + dt \simeq 1.29 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ s}, \quad (38)$$

$$\text{Earth} : \Delta\tau_{ET(-)}' = -dt \sqrt{\frac{\omega^2 r_3^2}{c^2}} + dt \simeq -4.3 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}, \quad (39)$$

and the discrepancy D_{ET} :

$$D_{ET} = -4.3 \cdot 10^{-9} + 1.29 \cdot 10^{-8} = 8.6 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}. \quad (40)$$

It means that, if it is taken as reference the time of the GPS clocks, that are in free fall in their orbit and therefore free from the terrestrial acceleration, after an hour of the terrestrial clock, the proper time will differ less of what expected. The above time interval is equal to about 2.57 m per hour.

Equivalence principle

From the equivalence principle, we got Eq. (18), which can be used to rewrite the Schwarzschild radius:

$$r_s = \frac{2G}{c^2} \cdot \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2 r}{G}, \quad (41)$$

$$r_s = 2r \cdot \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2}{c^2} = 2r\beta^2 \Rightarrow \frac{r_s}{r} = 2\beta^2, \quad (42)$$

where:

$$\beta = \frac{v}{c}. \quad (43)$$

and as the term $\frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}$ is equal to $\frac{v^2}{c^2}$, we can re-write Eq. (26):

$$d\tau = \pm dt \sqrt{1 - 3\beta^2}. \quad (44)$$

Space–time precession

The perfect balance between centrifugal and gravitational field, according to the present model, gives a flat space–time. Until now, however, it has not been considered yet the relativistic precession of the space–time, that was predicted by Albert Einstein to explain the anomalous precession of Mercury's perihelion.

The relativistic equation of the precession is:

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{6\pi GM}{c^2 A(1 - e^2)}, \quad (45)$$

where A = is the semi major axis of the orbit, e the orbit eccentricity, G the Newton's constant and c the speed of light. In the case of a circular motion, the equation can be simplify: the eccentricity e goes to 0 and A becomes equivalent to r . Dividing numerator and denominator of the equation for $2GM/c^2$, we get:

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{6\pi GM}{c^2 A(1 - e^2)} \cdot \frac{c^2}{2GM} = 3 \cdot \pi \frac{r_s}{r} = 6 \cdot \pi \beta^2. \quad (46)$$

It can be further simplified by dividing it for 2π . In this way, the ratio between the precession and a 2π rotation, provide the percentage respect to a full rotation.

$$\frac{\Delta\phi}{2\pi} = \frac{6 \cdot \pi}{2 \cdot \pi} \beta^2, \quad (47)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\phi}{2\pi} = 3\beta^2. \quad (48)$$

If a positive curvature gets a positive effect on the perihelion precession for a free fall body, a negative curvature should be the origin of a recession of the same value but opposite sign.

To state that a centrifugal acceleration leads to a recession of the space–time, is equivalent to postulate an expansion of the space–time. This hypothesis could be a very good candidate to explain the cosmological constant [9].

Unstable particle's lifetime

The radioactive elements are natural clocks automatically tuned on the Earth's proper time by the Nature.

In the present model, we suggest that in an infinitesimal amount of time, it is not possible to define a time direction and that, to be or not to be in an inertial reference frame, cannot make any difference.

The particles, from the other side, must obey to the Heisenberg's uncertainty principle where time and energy are bounded by the relation:

$$\Delta t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2\Delta E}. \quad (49)$$

For a stable particles, the concept of 'past' or 'future' is not well defined and they are free to move 'timeless' in a 'flat space-time'. Under these circumstances, General Relativity appear to be useless, however, it is not entirely true, because even if the time cannot tell where the particle is, the reference system confines her.

In the paper published by Matthews and Abdus Salam in the 1959 [10], they claim: "The only difference between the stable and the unstable case lies in the fact that fields corresponding to stable particles possess asymptotic limits, so that "in" and "out" fields can be defined.² This is not true for the unstable case."

The effect of a noninertial reference frame is therefore the best opportunity to investigate the theories, when particles manifest an unstable behavior.

After the discover of Mössbauer [12] in the 1958 of the nuclear resonance of gamma radiation in an accelerated system, many experiments have been done. In some cases, an excess of energy has been found but, the results, have been controversial, both for experimental and theoretical reasons [13–16].

It is therefore possible to evaluate the prediction of the present model in the case of the Mössbauer effect.

The source (S1) is placed in the arm of the centrifugal machine, while the absorber is at rest respect to the laboratory. A second source (S2) of the same mass and radioactivity, may eventually kept at rest in the laboratory, as second sample to double check the experimental results.

Once get the virtual mass and the relevant Schwarzschild radius through Eq. (20) and (21), it is possible to evaluate the radioactivity decay in the standard way:

$$N_t = N_0 e^{-\lambda t}, \quad (50)$$

where N_t is the atom number after a time $t = dt$, N_0 is the initial atoms number and λ the decay constant of the element.

$$S1 : \quad \tau_{1/2} = -t_{1/2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s^*}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}, \quad (51)$$

$$S1 : \quad d\tau = -dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s^*}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r_1^2}{c^2}}. \quad (52)$$

The coefficient under the square root is < 1 , therefore $|\tau_{1/2}| < -t_{1/2}$ and $|d\tau| < dt$.

$$S1 : \quad \lambda_1 = -\frac{\ln(2)}{\tau_{1/2}^*}, \quad (53)$$

$$S2 : \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{\ln(2)}{t_{1/2}}, \quad (54)$$

$|\lambda_1| > \lambda_2$ as $\ln(2)$ is a constant and $|\tau_{1/2}| < t_{1/2}$.

$$S1 : \quad N_{dt^*} = N_0 e^{-(\lambda_1^*)(-dt^*)}, \quad (55)$$

$$S2 : \quad N_{dt} = N_0 e^{-\lambda_2 dt}. \quad (56)$$

The half-life and the proper time are negative, but the entropy direction does not change. It is well understandable, since the exponent of (e) is still negative. The relativistic coefficient, however, does not lead to any change in the particle's decay life, since

it works equally on λ , $d\tau$ and $\tau_{1/2}$, at least until a limit of the velocity $v = c\sqrt{1/3}$ is reached. The radioactivity, instead, change significantly:

$$S1 : |Bq_1| = -\lambda^* N_0 e^{-(\lambda_1^*)(-dt^*)} \simeq Bq_2, \quad (57)$$

$$S2 : Bq_2 = \lambda N_0 e^{-\lambda_2 dt}. \quad (58)$$

Since $|\lambda_1^*| > \lambda_2$ and $N_{dt^*} = N_{dt}$, follows that:

$$Bq_2 - Bq_1 > 2Bq_2. \quad (59)$$

The negative activity has not to surprise since, according to the general idea of the present study, it is a consequence of the space-time field, due to the inversion of the event orders. What is negative, is the curvature of the space-time, as a consequence of the change of the reference frame system.

The energy of the photon emitted by S2, at rest, is equal to:

$$E_{S2} = \frac{hc}{\lambda}, \quad (60)$$

where λ = wave lengths of the γ photon. In special relativity the doppler effect for a moving source in the direction of the observer, is given by the equation:

$$\lambda' = \lambda \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}, \quad (61)$$

while, in the case of the Mössbauer effect, in an accelerated system, the equation, as a consequence of Eq. (59), should be:

$$\lambda' = 2 \cdot \lambda \sqrt{1 - 3\beta^2}, \quad (62)$$

$$E'_{S1} = \frac{hc}{2 \cdot \lambda} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 3\beta^2}}, \quad (63)$$

therefore, the total anomalous effect, in the Mössbauer experiment, is:

$$\Delta E'_{S1} = \frac{hc}{2 \cdot \lambda} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 3\beta^2}} \right). \quad (64)$$

The consequence leads to an equivalent effect between a moving source at constant linear velocity and a rotating disk at constant speed, according to the following equation:

$$k\lambda \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} = \lambda \sqrt{1 - 3\beta^2}, \quad (65)$$

where $k = \sqrt{1 - 3\beta^2} / \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$

$$\vec{v}' = \frac{\vec{v}}{k} \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}. \quad (66)$$

This model is similar to the phenomenology explained by Mössbauer, however it leads to a different results in the case of an accelerated reference system.

The subject of quantum interaction in different time frames, has been also treated from Hossenfelder [17]. The author has shown that, in such a case, is possible to preserve the causality.

Space-time transformation

In the previous section it has been made reference to speed limit equal to $c\sqrt{1/3}$. The reason of that can be seen from the Eq. (44):

$$d\tau = \pm dt \sqrt{1 - 3\beta^2}. \quad (67)$$

² Lehmann, Symanzik, and Zimmermann, (1955) [11].

When β^2 is equal to $1/3$ of c , $3\beta^2 = 1$ and, since the ratio $r_s/r = 2\beta^2$, the radius r is equal to $1.5r_s$. The term under the square root becomes equal to 0.

Apparently, we have reached an horizon, that cannot be overcome.

M. Abramowicz and R. Prasanna, [18] found that below a distance equal to $3M$ ($1.5r_s$) the centrifugal force becomes attractive.

The problem is very interesting because it does not involve only the results of the present work, but also the black holes.

From the other side we know, through high energy experiments, that particles can indeed accelerated to a tangential speed very close to the speed of light and that, stable particles like the proton, could not decay according to the standard model [8,19].

To solve the puzzle, we suggest to consider the effect of the precession and of the recession. We can consider the precession like the backreaction of the space–time under the effect of an orbiting body. From Eq. (46) we have got that the value of the precession is equal to $3 \cdot \pi \frac{r_s}{r}$. Such backreaction of the space–time, must be present also when the body is subject to a centrifugal acceleration, because, a space–time curvature of an opposite sign, must be present.

The points P_1 and P_2 (Fig. 6) have to be intended as the displacement of the point P due to the action of the precession/recession angle. The angles counterclockwise are positive. The resulting vectors of the acceleration R_{ct} and R_{cf} are: $R_{ct} = ct_2 - ct_1$ and $R_{cf} = ct_1 - ct_2$ where $\|ct_1\| = \|ct_2\|$ and $\|R_{ct}\| = \|R_{cf}\|$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{R_{ct}} \\ y_{R_{ct}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} -\cos d\phi \\ \sin d\phi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 + \cos d\phi \\ -\sin d\phi \end{pmatrix}, \quad (68)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{R_{cf}} \\ y_{R_{cf}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos d\phi \\ \sin d\phi \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \cos d\phi \\ \sin d\phi \end{pmatrix}, \quad (69)$$

and the modulus of the resulting vector R is:

$$R = \|\sqrt{2ct^2(1 - \cos d\phi)}\|, \quad (70)$$

where $\|R\| = \|R_{ct}\| = \|R_{cf}\|$ (Fig. 8).

Now, it is considered the case of a particle in a high energy circular accelerator, where it can reach a relativistic speed.

When $\beta^2 = 1/3$, the angle displacement of the acceleration vector is equal to $\|\Delta\phi\| = 2\pi$ and, it means, that both positions of a moving point at a speed of $c\sqrt{1/3}$, are equally true or, said in another way, they have the same probability to be true.

If the particle overcome the apparent horizon given by the speed of $c\sqrt{1/3}$ (it is a matter of fact it happens as far as the velocity is not zero and the limit of the light speed has not reached yet), of a quantity equal to $d\beta^2$, the recession angle $\Delta\phi$ increase of a quantity $3d\beta^2$. By doing that, it is in a second half of the circumference or, in other words, it is entering into the ‘precession zone’.

The vectors have been transported by the space–time in a new sector, where the precession is equal to $\Delta\phi = \pi - 3d\beta^2$. By increasing the speed of $2d\beta^2$, the recession will increase again and, therefore, the equivalent precession will be $\Delta\phi = \pi - 6\beta^2$ and so on.

The limit of $c\sqrt{1/3}$ is therefore an inflection point beyond which, the curvature, change of sign. Locally, the curvature vanishes.

From Table 1 we see that the acceleration becomes equal to zero for both components when the precession is a multiple of 2π . The space–time is flat. The coefficient under the square root is equal to 0, as well as dt .

More increases the tangential speed and the more the ‘precession’ decrease with the time. The entropy, however, still increases.

Fig. 6. Diagram of the acceleration vector displacement due to the space–time in the case of precession or recession.

We have divided the space–time in three sectors, one per each change of precession / recession (see Tables 2 and 3). When the sector is changing, to keep track of the time flow and of the circumference completion (see s coefficient of Table 1), the unit inside the square root must be increased of 1 as a consequence of the sign change of dt , as it is depicted in Fig. 7.

The Schwarzschild solutions are listed in Table 4]. The Schwarzschild solution in the 3rd sector, give also the solution in the case of the light, when $c = 1$, if we consider the equivalence principle ($r_s/r = 2\beta^2$, $\omega^2 r^2/c^2 = \beta^2$ and $\beta^2 = 1$) (42):

$$d\tau = \pm dt \sqrt{3 - 2\beta^2 - \beta^2} = 0. \quad (71)$$

The consequences are very interesting. In the sector II, the gravity becomes repulsive, while the centrifugal acceleration is attractive.

The reason of the centrifugal acceleration inversion, at a distance of $3M$ from the center of mass of a black hole, it is therefore, in the frame of the present analysis, a consequence of the space–time precession (Table 1).

The solution proposed in the graphic Fig. 7 is compatible with the geometry of the Möbius strip and, it suggests, that a torsion of the space–time, could be taken into consideration in concomitance to the precession [20–23]. The particles, in such a way, have the possibility to pass the continuum of the space–time without any discontinuity. What is changing violently, are the forces, due to the fields inversion.

This a process, in the case of star collapse, could justify the enormous and sudden release of energy that happens in a supernova explosion.

Such a model may also potentially explain why the proton becomes unstable at high energy. To test the life of the proton in a particle accelerator, before and after the threshold of the tangential speed of $v = c\sqrt{1/3}$, it is a concrete possibility, given the modest energy required, and the extreme performances that can be reached in the today’s circular particle accelerators.

This approach would be much more reliable and accurate that in any other experiment to verify tiny discrepancies in the Mössbauer effect.

One of the characteristic that distinguish the centrifugal acceleration from the gravitational one, is that the centrifugal acceleration has a maximum at the equator, while at the poles tends to zero. The gravity, on the contrary, has spherical symmetry. The physics of sector II, could also explain why, black holes, tend to accumulate the matter around their equatorial line and they expel particle jets from the poles.

Table 1

Relations between precession (and recession), radius and mass at some typical values of the ratio r/M . For values of $r/M < 1$, the velocity becomes superluminal.

r/M	Angle $d\phi$	s $d\phi/2\pi$	(v^2/c^2) β^2	Precession $x_{R_{ct}}$	Precession $y_{R_{ct}}$	Recession x_{R_d}	Recession y_{R_d}
1/2	37.70	6.0	2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1	18.85	3.0	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1 1/2	12.57	2.0	2/3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	9.42	1.5	1/2	-2.00	0.00	2.00	0.00
3	6.28	1.0	1/3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	3.14	0.5	1/6	-2.00	0.00	2.00	0.00

Table 2

Relations between the precession angle $\Delta\phi/2\pi$, the ratio M/r ($M = Gm/c^2$) and the radius r .

Sector	Precession s	Radius r	$M/r = \beta^2$
Sector I	$0 < s \leq 1$	$\infty > r \geq 3.0 M$	$0 < \beta^2 \leq 1/3$
Sector II	$1 < s \leq 2$	$3.0 M > r \geq 1.5 M$	$1/3 < \beta^2 \leq 2/3$
Sector III	$2 < s \leq 3$	$1.5 M > r \geq 1.0 M$	$2/3 < \beta^2 \leq 1$

Table 3

Relations between the instantaneous recession angle $\Delta\phi/2\pi$, the ratio M/r ($M = Gm/c^2$) and the radius r .

Sector	Recession s	Radius r	$M/r = \beta^2$
Sector I	$0 > s \geq -1$	$\infty > r \geq 3.0 M$	$0 < \beta^2 \leq 1/3$
Sector II	$-1 > s \geq -2$	$3.0 M > r \geq 1.5 M$	$1/3 < \beta^2 \leq 2/3$
Sector III	$-2 > s \geq -3$	$1.5 M > r \geq 1.0 M$	$2/3 < \beta^2 \leq 1$

It is also important to underline that the acceleration tend to 0 at the end of each sector. This happen equally both to the centrifugal acceleration that for the gravitational one.

We suggest, therefore, that the limit of the sector III can potentially remove the pathological singularity from the center of mass of black holes, thanks to the limit of c , when $r = M$.

Discussion

The present study is based on phenomenological aspects of the centrifugal acceleration trough the extension of the equivalence principle.

The inversion of the event orders, in the limit of the present analysis, does not seem to lead paradoxes but, instead, may suggest a novel way to investigate the particle's decay life and the symmetries CPT, in relation also to the ratio v/c .

Table 4

Summary of the suggested solution for sectors I, II and III. According to the equivalence principle, we found that $r_s/r = 2\beta^2$, while $\omega^2 r^2/c^2 = \beta^2$. At the end of each sector (Fig. 7), the coefficient under the square root of the Schwarzschild solution go to 0. The values of the radius, speed and precession angle are listed in Tables 2 and 3.

Sector	Gravitational acceleration	Centrifugal acceleration
Sector I	$d\tau = +dt\sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}$	$d\tau = -dt\sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}$
Sector II	$d\tau = -dt\sqrt{2 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}$	$d\tau = +dt\sqrt{2 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}$
Sector III	$d\tau = +dt\sqrt{3 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}$	$d\tau = -dt\sqrt{3 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{\omega^2 r^2}{c^2}}$

In the last section, our analysis has been driven by the precession and the recession phenomena to develop the space–time transformation rules. It is important to note that we did not considered the precession (and the recession) in an instantaneous rest frame.

The general theory of relativity, in a curved space, can be solved only if we can use the formalism of the special relativity. This means that the quadri-dimensional section of space–time must be considered small enough to approximate the space–time flat such that, the acceleration vanishes.

Of course, such condition, is exactly contrary to the aim we were going to achieve by considering the effect of the precession on the acceleration. It is obvious that, if the acceleration vanishes, such a research would loose meaning.

That is why, in our opinion, we must consider the precession after a full revolution of an orbiting point. It is also clear that in absence of a full revolution, the precession is undetermined as it becomes impossible to measure. We need to fix our reference system in very far quasars if we wish to consider the relative motion of the perihelion of our planet respect to the sun and, it can be measured, just after a full revolution.

Fig. 7. In this sketch we have divided the space–time in three sectors. At the end of each sector, the coefficient under the square root of the Schwarzschild solution goes to 0 and, the space–time reference frame, is reversed. In the new sector, $d\tau$ and $\Delta\tau$ exchange their sign. See also the values listed in Tables 2–4.

Fig. 8. Graphs show the trend of the acceleration and velocity vectors when the effect of precession and recession is added.

A similar situation can be found when we try to measure the wave length of a ray of light. The wave length is undetermined if we consider a time interval minor of the light frequency ($t = 1/\nu$).

The acceleration without mass cannot exist and, if the acceleration is missing, also the relativistic precession disappears. Similarly we can argue that the mass, without precession, cannot be defined.

Mass, precession and acceleration are tied in an indissoluble way. Under this point of view, is interesting to note that, a photon, has a perfect circular motion at a radius of $3M$ from the mass center of a black hole, where the acceleration vectors cancel each other and, as a consequence, the mass must be null (Table 1 and Fig. 8).

We have considered the consequences of the model in many different field of applications, and we have not found any evident contradictions.

The advantage of this simple model is the testability and, if confirmed, it could open a new door to investigate the Nature's symmetries.

Conclusion

We have considered three possible different way to prove the present study:

1. To test the clocks in a centrifugal fields.
2. To test the Mössbauer effect.
3. To test, the life time of the proton, in a circular particle accelerator.

We have also made a prediction on a possible systematic errors in the GPS coordinates. All points are very well testable and, we believe, they are a very good opportunity to verify the Nature's laws.

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